

JET FANS EFFICIENCY IN TUNNEL EMERGENCY SITUATIONS

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ABSTRACT. Tunnel construction has become an important and growing activity. Tunnelling is an important part of transport infrastructure and is a part of the sustainable development of the country. The tunnel ventilation during construction and operation is part of the whole design procedure. Although ventilation might be performed with different approaches, longitudinal ventilation with jet fans is most often employed. The efficiency of such devices depends on several factors – design parameters, location in the tunnel, interaction with main current. The last one is crucial in emergency situations, especially during fires when both temperature and density of main current change. One important point in normal and emergency ventilation design is the downwind influence of jet fans. This paper presents a longitudinal scheme with jet fans. Based on energy and mass conservation, the interaction between the jet fan and the main current is considered, leading to expressions for areas of impact. Several models for fire temperature distribution downstream are presented, outcomes are compared and suggestions for use are made. Additionally, jet fan efficiency coefficients are adjusted due to modelling results.

Keywords: jet fans, longitudinal ventilation, jet fan efficiency, road tunnels

Introduction

Recently, road traffic has been increasing and, at the same time, requirements for quality of road conditions has also been increasing. Under such circumstances, it is worth constructing new tunnels as part of the infrastructure and rehabilitate existing ones. Bulgarian road facilities, being part of the trans-European system, have to comply with EU and national regulations (Naredba № RD-02-20-2). An important part of the said regulations concerns tunnel ventilation, the main goals being to withdraw exhaust products out of the tunnel, to maintain safe atmosphere inside the tunnel, and last but not least - to ensure safe evacuation and accident damage mitigation. Tunnels longer than 400 m should have mechanical ventilation, which may be achieved in different ways (Vlasseva, 2015) – longitudinal, transverse and semi-transverse. Longitudinal ventilation with jet fans is increasingly being employed nowadays for several reasons: reduced construction costs since there is no need for additional air inlet and outlet devices, no need for special infrastructure close to tunnel portals and special, costly, ventilation technique. At the same time, jet fan industry is successfully developing in terms of design, improved efficiency, sizing, and power. The required ventilation power at the design stage is part of the whole project. Different types of jet fans provide more possibilities for ventilation and choice of the most suitable devices for the given tunnel. Proper operation of installed power depends on several factors, some of which are discussed in this paper: interaction between jet fan and main current, influence of extreme conditions in the tunnel (such as fire), adjustment of rated efficiency of jet fans to real conditions. All of the above-mentioned makes tunnelling an important part of the traffic infrastructure of our country. Correct design and realisation reduce the construction and operational costs which significantly contributes to the sustainable development of the country.

Jet Fans' Characteristics

Fig. 1 presents a typical jet fan design. The rotor is with symmetrical or asymmetrical blade profile. The models with symmetrical profile facilitate fan reversion, which makes them suitable for maintaining different current directions. The motors are 2 or 3-phase, reversible or non-reversible. The bearings

are self-lubricating. The silencers are with double lining and the inner part is a perforated metal surface filled with noise-absorption material.

Mounting may be fixed or hinged depending on the installation place. Constructions with deflection blades at different angles and anticorrosion protection with galvanisation are available.

Fig. 1. Jet fan construction

Jet fans' manufacturing characteristics include many parameters, which vary with producers. Some fan features, in relation to the problems discussed in this paper, include:

- Length, mm;
- Diameter (inner and outer), mm;
- Thrust, N;
- Power, kW;
- Velocity of outlet jet, m/s;
- Manufacturing effectiveness.

Jet fan producers offer a wide spectrum of dimensions and characteristics: wheel diameters from 350 to 1800 mm; power ratings from 13 to 100 kW; thrust range from 180 to 3000 N; velocity of outlet jet from 28 to 42 m/s. Effectiveness is approximately 0,87 – 0,85.

The jet kinetic energy of the fan transforms into kinetic energy of slow adjusting current, which causes the static pressure to rise. The jet expands, mixes with the main current, thus intensifying the tunnel flow. The distance downwind of the jet fan location, when this intensification takes place, is discussed below.

Theoretical Basis of Jet Fan Performance

In order to estimate the jet fan operation, air flows in a sector with jet fans are analysed. Fig. 2 shows the general layout of the section where:

- f_t, u_t - tunnel cross section [m²] and velocity [m/s] of main current;
- f_j, u_j - outlet cross section of jet fan [m²] and outlet jet velocity [m/s];
- L_1, L_2, L_{12} - distances ante- and post- jet fan location and total distance of the sector [m].

Fig. 2. Tunnel sector with a Jet fan

The real flow in a sector with jet fan is three dimensional. One two-dimensional top view is shown on Fig. 3. The distance in zone (IV) is where the jet from a fan loses its identity and mixes with the main tunnel flow.

Fig. 3. Velocity profile downwind the fan

One structural model is presented here (Kuda et al., 1999), based on:

- mass and energy conservation of both currents;
- jet fan energy conservation;
- pressure losses' balance.

It is assumed that the air densities of main and secondary flows are nearly the same ($\rho_j \approx \rho_t$). Further, when there is a process which leads to a change in the density, it will be included in the analysis. Impulse conservation [N] is presented with the following expression:

$$(P_2 - P_1)f_t = \rho_t f_t u_t^2 - \rho_j f_j u_j^2 - \rho^1 (f_t - f_j) u_t^2 + \frac{1}{2} \lambda \rho_2 \frac{\Delta x}{D_t} \bar{u}_t^2 f_t \quad [N] \quad (1)$$

where \bar{u}_t is the average velocity in the tunnel at a distance Δx downwind the fan.

According to the graph on Fig. 3, average velocity depends on jet expansion with distance. One approximation is given in Mutama (1995):

$$\bar{u}_j = k \frac{D_j}{x} u_j \quad (2)$$

where k is the mixing coefficient.

Fig. 4. Average velocity in the tunnel downwind the fan

Fig. 4 presents the average velocity, calculated by (2) with the following data: tunnel cross section $f_t = 73 \text{ m}^2$; hydraulic diameter $D_t = 7 \text{ m}$; diameter and cross section of jet fan outlet $d_j = 917 \text{ mm}$; $f_j = 0.4 \text{ m}^2$. It is clearly seen that, at the distance of 35-40 m downwind the fan, the average velocity equals 2 m/s – velocity of the tunnel flow before the jet fan operation. The average velocity is one part of the problem. It is more important to include the pressure changes due to the jet fan operation, on the one side, and friction pressure losses, on the other. Mass conservation law (3) is applied and u_t' (fig. 2) is expressed (formula 4):

$$\rho_t u_t' f_t = \rho_t u_t (f_t - f_j) + \rho_j u_j f_j \quad [kg / s] \quad (3)$$

$$u_t' = \frac{\rho_t u_t f_t - \rho_j u_j f_j}{\rho_t (f_t - f_j)} \quad (4)$$

Adding the local losses of jet fan inlet / outlet and combining with expression (1) gives (Kempf, 1965):

$$(P_2 - P_1)f_t = \rho_j f_j u_j^2 + \frac{1}{2} \rho_t u_t'^2 (f_t - 2f_j) - \frac{1}{2} \rho_t u_t'^2 \left(2 \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2} - 1 \right) f_t - \left(\zeta_d + \frac{1}{2} \lambda \frac{\Delta x}{D_t} \right) \frac{\rho_2}{2} \bar{u}_t^2 f_t \quad [N] \quad (5)$$

where: ζ_d – dimensionless friction coefficients of jet fan inlet/outlet;

λ - dimensionless friction coefficients of tunnel walls.

Expression (5) takes into account all parameters of composite flows. The maximum pressure achieved by a jet fan is published in Beyer at al. (2016):

$$\Delta P_{t,theo} = \rho u_j^2 \frac{f_j}{f_t} \left(1 - \frac{u_t}{u_j} \right) \quad (6)$$

Fig. 5 shows the difference between (5) and (6).

Fig. 5. Comparison of maximum (6) and real (5) pressure

Further, the density of flow in the vicinity of fan operation should be defined. Air density depends on temperature. The temperature in the tunnel could change rapidly due to tunnel fire. The next part of the paper deals with the average temperature evaluation downwind the fire along the tunnel length.

Temperature of fire gases of tunnel fire

Different expressions for calculation of the average temperature of fire gases are published in specialised references (CETU, 2003; Lonermark, 2005; PIARC, 2007; DelRey, 2012). Some of them pay special attention to additional mass and composition of fire gases (Yotova et al., 2017). All expressions are based on energy conservation of mass flow, which gives the relation between the fire effective power and the flow parameters:

$$Q_c = \dot{m} c_p (T - T_o) = \rho u f c_p (T - T_o), W \quad (7)$$

where: $Q_c = 2/3 Q'_c$ [W] Part of HRR (Heat Release Rate) which is transferred by convection and radiation;

$$\dot{m} = \rho u f \left[\frac{kg}{s} \right] \text{ mass flow;}$$

T, T_o [K] – fire source temperature and temperature before the fire starts.

Maximum temperature of fire source is obtained from (7):

$$T_{max} = T_o + \frac{Q_c}{\rho u f c_p} \quad (8)$$

The average temperature downwind the fire depends on the heat losses due to convection and radiation. These heat flows are as follows:

$$\text{Convection } q_c = h_c (T - T_{wall}), \frac{W}{m^2} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Radiation } q_r = \varepsilon \sigma (T^4 - T_o^4) = h_r (T^4 - T_o^4), \frac{W}{m^2} \quad (9a)$$

where: ε - wall emission capacity;

$\sigma = 5,68 \cdot 10^{-8}$ [(W/(m²K⁴))] - Stefan-Boltzmann constant

$h_c, \frac{W}{m^2 K}$ - convective heat exchange coefficient.

The overall heat flow is the sum of (9) and (9a):

$$q'' = h_c (T - T_{wall}) + h_r (T^4 - T_o^4) \left[\frac{W}{m^2} \right] \quad (10)$$

In (CETU, 2003; PIARC, 2007) h_c is calculated by the expression (11):

$$h_c = \frac{\frac{\lambda}{8} c_p \rho u^*}{1,07 + 12,7 (\text{Pr}^{2/3} - 1) \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{8}}} \quad (11)$$

where: λ - dimensionless friction coefficients of tunnel walls.

c_p – specific heat capacity; [J/kgK];

ρ - air density, [kg/m³];

u^* - air velocity at distance x downwind the fire $u(x)$; [m/s];

Pr – Prandl number.

Lonermark (2005) proposes an expression, where the distance x and Reynolds number take part:

$$h_c = 0,026 \text{Re}^{-0,2} \left\{ 1 + \left[\frac{D_H}{x} \right]^{0,7} \right\} \rho c_p u^* \quad (12)$$

where: Re – Reynolds number;

D_H – hydraulic diameter; [m];

After several calculations with the above expressions (9-12) some important clarifications are made:

- In (11) and (12) the velocity denoted as u^* should be recalculated for each distance downwind the fire, depending on the air density at this place $u^*(x) = \frac{\rho_o}{\rho(x)} u_o$;
- In (11) the Prandl number (Pr) changes depending on the temperature (Fig. 6);

Fig.6. Pr number vs temperature

- In (12) the Reynolds number should be recalculated with the changeable kinematic viscosity ($\nu(x, T)$) (Fig.7) and also with the already discussed velocity u^* .

Fig.7. Kinematic viscosity vs temperature

The results obtained under (11) and (12) show small differences, but use of (12) is more appropriate for more accurate reflection of the convective heat transfer based on the Reynolds number, the hydraulic diameter D_H , and the distance downwind the fire.

After the above clarifications, the heat balance equation is written (CETU, 2003; Lonermark, 2005; PIARC, 2007):

$$-\frac{1}{4} D_H \rho c_p u^* \frac{dT}{dx} = h_c (T - T_o) + \varepsilon \sigma (T^4 - T_o^4) \quad (13)$$

From (13) $\frac{dT}{dx}$ can be expressed:

$$\frac{dT}{dx} = -\frac{h_c(T - T_o) + \varepsilon\sigma(T^4 - T_o^4)}{\frac{1}{4}D_H\rho c_p u^*} \quad (14)$$

One iterative solution can be obtained with discretisation of the tunnel length in small steps Δx and the corresponding indexes:

$$L_{fire} \leq x_i \leq L_{tunnel}; x_{i+1} = x_i + \Delta x \quad (15)$$

Applying the above, the discretisation (14) can be written in the following way:

$$\frac{dT_i}{dx_i} = -\frac{h_c(i-1)(T(x_{i-1}) - T_o) + \varepsilon\sigma(T^4(x_{i-1}) - T_o^4)}{\frac{1}{4}D_H\rho_{i-1}c_p u_{i-1}^*} \quad (16)$$

Expression (16) gives the formula for temperature change evaluation in an interval Δx . Then the value of the temperature in the next interval is calculated:

$$T_{i+1} = T_i + \Delta T_{i+1} \quad (17)$$

Another approximation of (13) is published in (DelRey, 2012; Beyer, 2012):

$$T(x) = T_o + (T(x - \Delta x) - T_o) e^{-\frac{4h_{app}}{\rho f D_H u^*}(x - x_{fire})} \quad (18)$$

$$h_{app} = \frac{\phi_c + \phi_x}{T - T_o}$$

where: ϕ_c , ϕ_x are convective and radiative heat flows [W].

Fig. 8 shows comparison of results obtained by (16) and (18) with the same data: 100 MW HRR takes place on the 400 m of the tunnel portal in a 1200 m tunnel. The analysis of the results leads to the following conclusion: the temperature calculated with (18) reaches the initial one (290K) only 200 m downwind the fire. This result doesn't correspond to real experiments, published by (Cafalo, 2010; Ingason, 2010), where fire influence is traced for longer distances, even to the other tunnel portal. That is why our recommendation is to use an iteration procedure (16), because at a project phase we should take into account a more realistic situation, rather than neglect the real danger. The required mechanical ventilation should be calculated based on accidental behaviour of the system.

Fig. 8. Comparison of results, obtained by (16) and (18)

Fig. 9 shows the velocity change downwind the fire by (16).

Fig. 9. Velocity change downwind the fire

Fig. 10 shows the density change downwind the fire. These two graphs (Fig. 9 and 10) are important with regard to the jet fan efficiency. This will be discussed in the next point.

Fig. 10. Density change downwind the fire

Jet fan efficiency in fire situation

Jet fans' manufacturing characteristics, as stated above, include the effectiveness coefficient η_{max} , based on laboratory tests. The real jet fan operation effectiveness differs due to several parameters:

- installation efficiency η_i (19) – depends on the relationship between the distance to the tunnel wall (z) and the outer fan diameter (D) – Fig. 11. Expression (19) is an approximation published in Tarada (2009), based on the experimental data obtained by Kempf (1965)

$$\eta_i = \left[0,0192 \left(\frac{z}{d} \right)^2 - 0,144 \frac{z}{d} + 1,27 \right]^{-1} \quad (19)$$

Fig. 11. Installation efficiency

- velocity effectiveness η_v – depends on the relationship between the main current and the outlet jet velocity;

$$\eta_v = 1 - \frac{u_t}{u_j} \quad (20)$$

- temperature effectiveness η_ρ - depends on the flow density.

$$\eta_\rho = \frac{\rho_t}{1.2} \quad (21)$$

The jet fan performance reflects all four coefficients (22):

$$\eta_{eff} = \eta_{max} \times \eta_i \times \eta_v \times \eta_\rho \quad (22)$$

An overall expression for the performance evaluation taking into account the required number of jet fans (n), in combination with (5), (20, and (21) is presented below:

$$\eta = 100 \frac{\Delta P_{12} + (\zeta_d + \lambda \frac{\Delta x}{D_t}) \frac{\rho}{2} u_t^2}{n \rho u_j^2 \frac{f_j}{f_t} (1 - \frac{u_t}{u_j})} \quad (23)$$

Discussion

The impact of flow parameters in case of tunnel fire on the jet fan operation is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Jet fan characteristics

Jet fan characteristics		
Thrust F_{JF}	1230	N
Outlet velocity u_{JF}	32.3	m/s
Diameter D_{JF}	1.2	m
Distance to tunnel ceiling z	0.5	m
Manufacturing efficiency η_{max}	0.88	-

Fig. 12 shows the velocity and temperature coefficients. It can be noticed that rapid decrease is observed in the vicinity of the fire source and 200 m downwind due to increase of the temperature and decrease of the density. Gradually, the coefficients become close to their initial values, but are not the same.

Fig. 12. Velocity and density efficiency

Fig. 13 shows the impact of fires with different HRR – 30, 50, 70 and 100 MW. Again, the biggest impact is 400 m downwind the fire. The conclusion is that, in these sectors, the jet fans will operate with lower effectiveness. In case of 30 MW

HRR, the performance decreases by 14%, while for 100 MW fire this reduction is 40 %. That means that our calculations based on the manufacturing effectiveness for the rated ventilation power should ensure reserves according to the methodology presented in this paper.

Fig. 13. Efficiency vs fire HRR

The obtained results once again confirm the rule for design of tunnel ventilation: it should be done based on design fires, located at different places inside the tunnel. Normal ventilation should use part of the overall capacity, enough to maintain the tunnel atmosphere within safety limits (Naredba № RD-02-20-2, 2015). Furthermore, the impact of the natural ventilation pressure on the mechanical ventilation should be analysed and taken into account in order to estimate fan reserves (Vlasheva and Dinchev, 2015).

Conclusion

The results of this study can be summarised as follows:

- based on the mass and impulse conservation laws, expressions for interaction between the jet fan operation and the main tunnel flow are proposed;
- as a result of the thorough analysis of all available expressions for average tunnel fire gases’ temperatures and all influencing parameters, one iteration procedure is recommended. Its results are compared to real experiments;
- special attention is paid to the adjustment of fan performance in extreme conditions.

Future research might be targeted towards the work of paired jet fans (2 or 3 in parallel) (Guihong, 2014), the use of special directional blades at the inlet/outlet of the jet fan, and additional consideration of the mass generated by the fire source.

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